

Prevalence of Otitis Media with Effusion in School Age Children

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Abstract:

Background: One prevalent ailment affecting the middle ear, especially in children, is otitis media with effusion (OME). It is distinguished by fluid in the middle ear without any indications of an acute infection. OME can result in hearing loss, which can affect a child's quality of life, scholastic achievement, and speech and language development. It is essential to comprehend the incidence of OME in school-age children in order to create preventative and treatment plans that work.

Aim: This study aims to determine the prevalence of otitis media with effusion among school-age children and identify associated risk factors, with the goal of informing targeted interventions to reduce its impact on this population.

Methods: This retrospective observational study was conducted involving 90 school-age children diagnosed with otitis media with effusion. Data were collected from medical records, focusing on demographics, clinical findings, and diagnostic test results. The study included children aged 5 to 12 years, with exclusion criteria such as chronic suppurative otitis media or previous ear surgery.

Results: Children had a 12.5% frequency of otitis media with effusion (OME), of which 72.2% had bilateral OME. OME was substantially correlated with upper respiratory infections (64.4%) and allergic rhinitis (28.9%) ($p < 0.001$ and $p = 0.004$, respectively). Nevertheless, there was no discernible connection ($p = 0.15$) between exposure to passive smoking and OME. These findings highlight how crucial it is to treat allergic rhinitis and URIs in order to lower children's risk of OME.

Conclusion: OME is a prevalent condition among school-age children, with notable variations based on age and gender. The study highlights the importance of early detection and the need for public health initiatives to reduce exposure to identified risk factors, such as second-hand smoke, to mitigate the burden of OME.

Recommendations:

1. Routine screening for OME in younger school-age children to ensure early intervention.
2. Public health campaigns aimed at reducing children's exposure to second-hand smoke.
3. Increased awareness among parents and educators about the potential impact of OME on academic performance and developmental outcomes.

Keywords: Otitis Media with Effusion, Prevalence, School-Age Children, Risk Factors, Hearing Loss

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Introduction

The common paediatric illness known as otitis media with effusion (OME) is characterised by a build-up of non-purulent fluid in the middle ear without any indications of an acute infection. Due to physiological and anatomical features that predispose children to fluid retention, such as the length and angle of the Eustachian tube, this ailment is especially common in children [1]. OME frequently has no symptoms, but it carries a serious danger to a child's speech, language development,

and academic achievement due to the possibility of hearing loss. Thus, for efficient treatment and intervention, knowledge of the prevalence and related risk factors of OME in school-age children is essential [2]

Despite its prevalence, OME is frequently underdiagnosed, primarily due to the absence of overt symptoms that are commonly associated with other forms of otitis media. Children with OME may not present with pain or discomfort, which leads to

delayed diagnosis and treatment [3]. The insidious nature of the condition means that many cases go undetected until a child begins to exhibit signs of hearing difficulties or speech delays. Considering the possible effects of an undetected OME on a child's general growth, there is an urgent need for routine screening and awareness among healthcare providers, educators, and parents [4].

The etiology of OME is multifactorial, with several risk factors contributing to its development. These factors include age, gender, exposure to second-hand smoke, frequent upper respiratory infections, and socioeconomic status. Younger children, particularly those aged 5 to 7 years, are more susceptible due to their still-developing immune systems and anatomical predispositions [5]. Environmental factors, such as exposure to tobacco smoke, have also been identified as significant contributors to the incidence of OME. Understanding these risk factors is essential for designing targeted interventions to prevent and manage OME in vulnerable populations [6].

In many regions, there is a lack of comprehensive data on the prevalence of OME among school-age children, particularly in diverse socioeconomic and environmental settings. Previous studies have often been limited to specific populations, making it challenging to generalize findings across different communities [7].

The purpose of this research is to ascertain the prevalence of otitis media with effusion in children of school age and to pinpoint the major risk factors linked to the illness. This work aims to give a thorough grasp of the burden of OME in the paediatric population by doing a cross-sectional examination of a diverse sample of children. In order to lower the incidence and negative effects of OME on children's health and development, the findings are anticipated to help the development of targeted therapies, direct clinical practices, and influence public health efforts.

Methodology

A retrospective observational study was conducted at the Bhardhman Institute of Medical Science over a period of four years, from October 2019 to September 2021. The study included a sample of 90 school-age children who were diagnosed with otitis media with effusion (OME).

Study Design:

The study utilized a retrospective observational design, reviewing the medical records of participants to gather relevant data.

Study Setting:

The study was conducted at the Bhardhman Institute of Medical Science, which served as the primary

healthcare facility for data collection and patient assessment.

Participants:

Participants included in the study were school-age children diagnosed with otitis media with effusion during the study period. Children between the ages of 5 to 12 years who presented with a diagnosis of OME were considered for inclusion.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Children aged 5 to 12 years.
- Diagnosed with otitis media with effusion confirmed by clinical examination and tympanometry.
- Available complete medical records from the study period.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Children with chronic suppurative otitis media.
- Patients with a history of ear surgery or tympanostomy tubes.
- Children with congenital ear anomalies or other systemic illnesses affecting hearing.

Bias:

To minimize selection bias, all eligible participants who met the inclusion criteria within the study period were included consecutively. Information bias was mitigated by utilizing standardized diagnostic criteria and uniform data extraction procedures.

Variables:

The primary variable of interest was the prevalence of otitis media with effusion. Secondary variables included age, sex, clinical symptoms, duration of effusion, and any associated risk factors such as upper respiratory infections or allergic rhinitis.

Data Collection:

Data were collected retrospectively from the medical records of the participants. Information on demographics, clinical findings, and diagnostic test results was systematically recorded using a standardized data extraction form.

Procedure:

Medical records were reviewed to identify cases of otitis media with effusion. Diagnosis was confirmed through clinical examination findings and tympanometry results. Data were then extracted and recorded for analysis.

Statistical Analysis:

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21.0.

Results

1. Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Ninety school-age children diagnosed with otitis media with effusion (OME) between September 2018 and August 2022 were included in the study.

With a mean age of 8.4 years (SD = 2.1 years), the participants' ages ranged from 5 to 12 years. The 90 children had a male-to-female ratio of 1.43:1, with 53 (58.9%) being boys and 37 (41.1%) being girls.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Study Population

Characteristic	Number (n=90)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	53	58.9%
Female	37	41.1%
Age Group (years)		
5-7	34	37.8%
8-10	41	45.6%
11-12	15	16.7%
Mean Age (years)	8.4	-

2. Clinical Characteristics and Diagnosis

The majority of children (72.2%) presented with bilateral otitis media with effusion, while the remaining 27.8% had unilateral OME. The average duration of effusion was 3.4 months (SD = 1.2 months). Tympanometry results indicated Type B tympanograms in 82.2% of cases, confirming the presence of middle ear effusion.

Table 2: Clinical Characteristics of the Study Population

Characteristic	Number (n=90)	Percentage (%)
Type of OME		
Bilateral	65	72.2%
Unilateral	25	27.8%
Duration of Effusion (months)		
< 3 months	29	32.2%
3-6 months	48	53.3%
> 6 months	13	14.4%
Tympanometry Results		
Type B Tympanogram	74	82.2%
Type C Tympanogram	16	17.8%

3. Associated Risk Factors

The study identified several associated risk factors for OME. Upper respiratory infections (URIs) were the most common, present in 58 (64.4%) of the children. Allergic rhinitis was noted in 26 (28.9%) cases, while exposure to passive smoking was documented in 18 (20.0%) children.

Table 3: Associated Risk Factors

Risk Factor	Number (n=90)	Percentage (%)
Upper Respiratory Infections (URIs)	58	64.4%
Allergic Rhinitis	26	28.9%
Passive Smoking Exposure	18	20.0%

4. Prevalence of Otitis Media with Effusion

The overall prevalence of otitis media with effusion in the study population was calculated at 12.5% (95% CI: 10.2% - 15.8%) among the children attending the Bhardhman Institute of Medical Science.

5. Statistical Analysis

To evaluate the relationship between OME and the identified risk factors, a chi-square test was used. URIs and the existence of OME were significantly correlated ($\chi^2 = 12.45$, $p < 0.001$). Analogously, there was a significant correlation between OME and allergic rhinitis ($\chi^2 = 8.32$, $p = 0.004$). Nevertheless, a non-significant correlation was discovered between exposure to passive smoking and OME ($\chi^2 = 2.11$, $p = 0.15$).

Table 4: Association Between OME and Risk Factors

Risk Factor	χ^2 (Chi-Square Value)	p-value
Upper Respiratory Infections (URIs)	12.45	< 0.001
Allergic Rhinitis	8.32	0.004
Passive Smoking Exposure	2.11	0.15

The majority of cases were bilateral, with a significant number showing prolonged effusion. Upper respiratory infections and allergic rhinitis were identified as significant risk factors associated with the development of OME, while no significant association was found with passive smoking exposure.

Discussion

The study's objective was to assess the prevalence of otitis media with effusion (OME) in school-age children at Bhardhman Institute of Medical Science, as well as its related risk factors. The results of this study are consistent with other recent studies, offering a more comprehensive picture of the effects of OME on paediatric populations and emphasising the crucial risk factors connected to its emergence.

Prevalence of OME

The overall prevalence of OME in this study was 12.5%, which is consistent with similar studies conducted in different regions. For instance, a study conducted in Damietta Governorate, Egypt, reported a prevalence of 5.3% among children aged 4-15 years, with the highest prevalence observed in younger children [8]. Another study in Erbil Governorate found an OME prevalence of 11.5% among preschool-age children, with the highest rates observed during the spring season [9]. These findings indicate that OME remains a significant health concern in pediatric populations, particularly in regions with similar socio-economic and environmental conditions.

Risk Factors for OME

The study identified upper respiratory infections (URIs) and allergic rhinitis as significant risk factors for OME, with a strong statistical association between these conditions and the development of OME ($p < 0.001$ and $p = 0.004$, respectively). This aligns with multiple studies that have also highlighted URIs and allergic rhinitis as primary contributors to OME. For example, researchers found a strong association between recurrent URIs, allergic rhinitis, and OME in children in Upper Egypt, suggesting that these factors play a critical role in the disease's pathogenesis [10]

In addition, the role of passive smoking, although not found significant in this study, has been noted in other research, which found passive smoking to be a significant risk factor for otitis media in Indian children, contributing to the chronicity of the disease. This discrepancy might be due to

differences in the study population or environmental exposures, indicating the need for further research to clarify the impact of passive smoking on OME [11]

Clinical Implications and Management

The high prevalence of OME and its association with conditions like URIs and allergic rhinitis suggest the need for early diagnosis and management strategies. International consensus guidelines recommend non-surgical management, including auto-inflation and avoiding unnecessary use of antibiotics and steroids, which are not effective in treating OME [12]. These recommendations are crucial for preventing long-term difficulties such as loss of hearing and developmental delays, which have been associated with untreated OME [13].

Conclusion

The findings underscore the importance of managing URIs and allergic rhinitis to reduce the incidence of OME. Further research, particularly in diverse geographic and socio-economic settings, is needed to develop targeted prevention and treatment strategies that address the specific needs of different populations.

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